

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND SELF-CONCEPT IN SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND ITS INFLUENCE ON EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT

Shilpa, Poonam

Master of Education (Student), Department of Education, BPSMV,
Khanpur Kalan, Haryana, India

Sandhya

Master of Arts-Education (Student), Department of Education, BPSMV,
Khanpur Kalan, Haryana, India

Dr. Sushil Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, BPSMV,
Khanpur Kalan, Haryana, India

ABSTRACT

This research paper explored the relationship between parental involvement and self-concept in secondary school students and its influence on educational adjustment. The role of parental involvement, which includes support, guidance, and participation in a child's education, is important in shaping how adolescents view themselves and how well they adjust in school. Self-concept refers to individuals' beliefs about themselves, has a significant impact on their academic performance, social interaction, and emotional well-being. Educational adjustment refers to academic success, school satisfaction, and social integration, which is affected by both parental involvement and self-concept. This study used quantitative method. The sample of 100 secondary schools students was selected from government and private schools located in the rural and urban areas of Sonipat district. Tool for collecting the data included Adjustment Inventory for School Students constructed and standardized by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh (1971) and Parental Involvement Scale developed and standardized by Dr. Vijay Laxmi Chouhan and Mrs. Gunjan Ganota Arora (2008) and Self Concept Scale developed and standardized by R. K. Saraswat (1984). The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

The findings of the study revealed that there is statistically significant positive relationship between parental involvement, self concept and educational adjustment among secondary school students.

Additionally, higher level of parental involvement and self-concept are associated with better educational adjustment among secondary school students.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Self-Concept, Educational Adjustment, Secondary School Students.

Cite this Article: Shilpa, Poonam, Sandhya, Sushil Kumar, Exploring The Relationship Between Parental Involvement and Self-Concept in Secondary School Students and Its Influence on Educational Adjustment, International Journal of Education (IJE), 5(1), 2024, pp. 24-32.

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJE?Volume=5&Issue=1>

INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in personal development and societal progress. It equips individuals with the necessary knowledge, skills, and critical thinking abilities to navigate the complexities of the modern world. The effectiveness of an education system however depends not only on the content and method of teaching but also on the interactive relationship between students, teachers, and families. Secondary school phase, which is important phase in a student's journey, during this stage students undergo significant changes in their thinking, social interaction, and emotions. Academic pressure intensify, relationship with peers become more significant, and students embark on a journey of self-discovery. Within the realm of education multiple factor significantly impact students' academic success, mental health, and overall adaptability in school. Among these parental involvement and self-concept are two key factors that are highly influential in shaping students' educational journey and results.

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

Parental involvement means involvement and contribution of parents or guardians in the education, upbringing and general development of their child. This involves a variety of activities and interactions between parents and schools, teachers and communities to support children's learning and well-being. This involvement can take many forms such as attending parent teacher conferences, volunteering in the classroom helping with homework, attending school events, responding to the child's needs and creating a home environment that is conducive to the child's learning.

DIMENSIONS OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

Epstein's framework for parental involvement outlines six dimensions of involvement:

1. Parenting: This includes creating a home environment that encourages learning. This includes things like setting up a routine, providing a quiet space to study, and talking to your child about school.
2. Communication: This includes effective communication between parents, teachers and students. This may include attending parent teacher conferences, regularly checking your child's online grade book and speaking with your child's teacher about any concern.
3. Volunteering at school: It refers to actively involved in school activities and events.
4. Learning at home: This includes assisting your child with their homework and school related tasks such as reading, test preparation and project completion.
5. Decision-making: Decision making involves parents playing a role in making decisions related to their child's education which may involve joining school committees, councils, or providing input on school policies.

6. Collaborating with community: Collaborates with community resources and organization to meet the educational and developmental needs of children outside of the school environment

SELF-CONCEPT

Self-concept is a person's perception and evaluation of themselves, including their beliefs, attitudes, and feeling about their identity, abilities and values. It is a central aspect of psychological development and plays an important role in shaping behavior, emotions, and interpersonal relationships.

DIMENSIONS OF SELF-CONCEPT

One of the prominent theorists who contributed to the understanding of self-concept is Carl Rogers, who proposed three dimension:

1. Self-image: This dimension concerns the way individuals perceive themselves, including their appearance, personality traits, abilities, and role in society.
2. Self-esteem: This dimension reflects a person's assessment of his or her own self-worth and value. This includes being confident, proud, and satisfied with your abilities and success.
3. Ideal self: This dimension represents a person's aspiration and goals. These includes individual's standards and expectations for their own behavior and outcome, which are often influenced by social norms and personal values.

EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT

Educational adjustment refers to the process by which students adapt to and overcome the demands and challenges of the educational environment. It includes various factors such as academic performance, social integration, and emotional well-being and overall academic success.

DIMENSIONS OF EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT

1. Academic performance: Academic performance refers to how well students meet academic standards and succeed in their studies.
2. Social integration: Social integration involves students' ability to form positive relationships with peers, teachers, and other social community members.
3. Emotional well-being: Emotional well-being focuses on students' emotional stability and ability to cope up with stress and other challenges in the school environment.
4. Motivation and engagement: Motivation and engagement are about the level of interest and commitment students show towards their learning and educational goals.
5. Behavioral adjustment: It refers to students' capability to follow school rules and manage their behavior effectively.
6. Cognitive and Learning skill: It encompass the development and use of cognitive abilities, learning strategies, and problem solving skills essential for academic achievement and continuous learning.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Monisha, B., & Vaidharani, V. S. (2024) studied on "Parental involvement and academic stress among higher secondary school students in Chennai district". This study aimed to investigate the relationship between academic stress and parental involvement among higher secondary school students.

Utilizing a sample of 200 students and their parents selected through incidental cum purposive sampling, the study employed the academic stress scale and parent involvement scale. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested. The findings indicating moderate academic stress level among students with the average parental involvement. Gender differences was not found between the level of stress and parental involvement. Both boys and girls had the same level of academic stress and parental involvement.

Rajput, P., & Bala, I. (2023) studied on “Relationship between educational adjustment and academic achievement among adolescents”. This study examined educational adjustment of secondary school students in Sonipat district, Haryana, India. It involved 100 students (50 boys, 50 girls) from both private and government schools. Results showed that students had an above average adjustment level, with girls slightly better adjusted than boys. There was no significant difference in adjustment based on school type. The study found a positive correlation between educational adjustment and academic achievement.

Gupta, G., & Priyanka (2022) studied on “A comparative study of self-concept of male and female secondary students of Panipat district”. This study used a descriptive survey method, 50 students were randomly selected and assessed using the Self-Concept Questionnaire by Dr. Raj Kumar Saraswat. Results indicated a high level of self-concept in both groups with no significant difference between genders.

Shao et al. (2022) conducted a study on “The influences of parental involvement on parent satisfaction: The moderating effect of parental educational level and the number of children.” This study is conducted through a descriptive survey among middle school students' parents in southern China, the study utilized a mediational analysis model for data analysis. The findings of the study was revealed that parental involvement have a positive correlation with parental satisfaction, and parental education level and the number of children both have a moderating role in predicting parental involvement and parental satisfaction. The study concluded that moderating effect of number of children in positive whereas the moderating effect of the educational level of parents is negative.

Misra, J., (2021) researched on “A study on the relationship between self-concept and self-confidence level of adolescent students”. This study examined self-concept and self-confidence in late adolescents (class 10th students) in Assam, India. Most students had high self- concept and above average self-confidence. The study found a positive correlation between self-concept and self-confidence.

Rajkumari & Babita (2021) researched on “A study of educational adjustment in relation to self-efficacy of secondary school students”. The study investigates educational adjustment and self-efficacy among 9th-grade secondary school students in Sonipat, Haryana. A sample of 100 students from government and private schools was randomly selected. Data collected using Adjustment Inventory and Self-efficacy Scale were analyzed using t-tests. Results reveal that female students exhibit lower educational adjustment than males, and government school students are less adjusted than private school students. No significant gender or school type differences were found in self-efficacy.

Singh, M., & Mahajan, P. (2021) researched on “Parental involvement and academic achievement: a study on senior secondary students”. This study examined the impact of parental involvement on academic achievement among senior secondary students in Jammu Tehsil, involving 200 randomly selected students. Utilizing the Parental Involvement scale by Chouhan and Arora (2008) and previous exam results, it found significant gender-based and locality-based differences in academic achievement and parental involvement. However, no disparity was observed between urban and rural students. Positive correlation were identified between parental involvement and academic achievement for both rural and urban students.

Tiwari, N. S., & Tiwari, S. K. (2020) researched on “Relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement in higher secondary school students”. This research investigated the correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement among higher secondary school students. Using a survey method with stratified random sampling, the study surveyed 100 XI class students from rural and urban schools in Umari District, Madhya Pradesh. The Parental Involvement scale by Dr. Vijaya Laxmi Chouhan and Mrs. Gunjan Ganotra Arora was employed, along with the academic achievement data from the students 10th grade annual examination. Result revealed a significant positive relationship between parental involvement and students’ academic achievement.

Adeyemi, B. A., Adediran, V. O., & Adewole, O. S. (2018) studied on “Influence of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupils’ adjustment in lower primary schools in Osun State”. This study investigated parental involvement in school adjustment among lower primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria, and examined the influence of parental socioeconomic status on this involvement. Utilizing a correlation research design with a sample size of 300 parents data were collected using the Parental involvement, Parental support and Family education on Pupils’ Adjustment Questionnaire (PIPSFEPAQ). Findings revealed a high level of parental involvement in school adjustment amount 36.6 % of respondent, with a significant correlation between home and school variable and parental involvement. This study concluded that creating a supportive home environment is crucial for promoting pupils adjustment in school.

Sekar, J., & Lawrence, A. S. (2016) researched on “Emotional, social, educational adjustment of higher secondary school students in relation to academic achievement. This study investigated the relationship between adjustment and academic achievement among higher secondary school students in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu, India. Using stratified random sampling based on gender and locality 350 students from 10 schools were selected. This study employed the adjustment inventory by A.K.P Sinha and R.P. Singh (2007) and an academic achievement measure analysis using called Pearson correlation coefficient revealed a significant relationship between emotional social and educational adjustment and academic achievement.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Education is an essential part of society as it enables the individual to achieve self-sufficiency and make a significant contribution to the development of their country. However, the educational process can’t be considered complete without the active participation of parents. The family unit which not only shapes the child’s future character but also forms the basis of his development, play the fundamental role in supporting socialization and in the formation of responsible individuals. It is the responsibility of the parents to guide their children, ensure their academic success and develop them into reliable citizens. As children transition into adolescence, parental influence tends to decrease due to various factors such as peer influence, mental distraction, and changes in the social system.

At this stage, one of the most important changes that young people experience is the development of their self-concept - the overall understanding of who they are their strengths and weakness, their values and their goals. The self-concept play a key role in shaping their educational experience and overall well-being. Keeping into consideration the significance of parental role and self-concept in defining and guiding the achievement level of adolescents, the present study is selected that is “Exploring the relationship between parental involvement and self-concept in secondary school students and its influence on educational adjustment”.

Objectives

1. To explore the relationship between parental involvement and self-concept among secondary school students.
2. To investigate the influence of parental involvement and self-concept on educational adjustment among secondary school students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relation between parental involvement and self-concept among secondary school students in Sonipat district.
2. There is no significant influence of parental involvement and self-concept on educational adjustment among secondary school students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey method was used in the present study.

Population

All secondary school students studying in various government and private schools of Sonipat district comprised the target population for the present study.

Sample

For the present study a sample of 100 (50 boys and 50 girls) students of 9th class studying in school Sonipat district.

Tools Used for Data Collection

1. Adjustment Inventory for School Students constructed and standardized by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh (1971).
2. Parental Involvement Scale developed and standardized by Dr. Vijay Laxmi Chouhan and Mrs. Gunjan Ganota Arora (2008).
3. Self-Concept Scale developed and standardized by R. K. Saraswat (1984).

Statistical Techniques Used

Descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard Deviations) and Inferential statistics (Correlation and regression) was used to analysis the data.

Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher collected the data personally with prior permission of the schools and concerned teachers. The administration of the tool viz., Adjustment Inventory for School Students by Sinha and Singh (1971), Parental Involvement Scale developed and standardized by Dr. Vijay Laxmi Chouhan and Mrs.

Gunjan Ganota Arora (2008) and Self Concept Scale developed and standardized by R. K. Saraswat (1984). was completed following the instructions given by the author of the tool.

DATA ANALYSIS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and self-concept among secondary school students.

Table: 1 Relationship between Parental Involvement and Self-Concept

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Parental Involvement	Self-Concept
Parental Involvement	100	87.44	11.48	1	0.214
Self-Concept	100	178.32	16.06	0.214	1

Correlation	r	p-value
Parental Involvement & Self-Concept	0.214	0.032

This table shows the correlation between parental involvement and self-concept among the 100 students. The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.214, indicating a weak positive relationship. The p-value of 0.032 suggests that this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and self-concept among secondary school students in this sample.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of parental involvement and self-concept on educational adjustment among secondary school students.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics:

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Educational Adjustment	100	4.83	3.53
Parental Involvement	100	87.44	11.48
Self-Concept	100	178.32	16.06

Table 3: Influence of Parental Involvement and Self-Concept on Educational Adjustment

Source	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p-value
Regression	2	487.26	243.63	11.96	<0.001
Residual	97	1973.71	20.35		
Total	99	2460.97			

Predictor Variables: Parental Involvement, Self-Concept

Outcome Variable: Educational Adjustment

Variable	B	Std. Error	β	t	p-value
(Constant)	-2.84	4.26		-0.67	0.507
Parental Involvement	0.13	0.04	0.31	3.24	0.002
Self-Concept	0.05	0.03	0.20	2.05	0.043

$$R = 0.435$$

$$R^2 = 0.189$$

$$\text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.173$$

The descriptive statistics as evident from table 2 provides the means and standard deviations for the educational adjustment, parental involvement, and self-concept variables.

The regression table 3 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis with parental involvement and self-concept as predictor variables and educational adjustment as the outcome variable.

The key findings from the regression analysis are:

1. The regression model is statistically significant ($F=11.96$, $p<0.001$), indicating that parental involvement and self-concept together significantly predict educational adjustment.
2. Both parental involvement ($\beta=0.31$, $p=0.002$) and self-concept ($\beta=0.20$, $p=0.043$) are significant positive predictors of educational adjustment.
3. The model explains 17.3% of the variance in educational adjustment (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.173$).

Based on these results, we can reject the null hypothesis "There is no significant influence of parental involvement and self-concept on educational adjustment among secondary school students."

The positive regression coefficients (B) for parental involvement (0.13) and self-concept (0.05) indicate that higher level of parental involvement and self-concept are associated with better educational adjustment among secondary school students.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers are thankful to everyone who took part in the study and recognizes their contribution in supporting the research paper.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. There is a significant relationship between parental involvement and self-concept among secondary school students.
2. There is significant influence of parental involvement and self-concept on educational adjustment among secondary school students. The positive regression coefficients indicate that higher level of parental involvement and self-concept are associated with better educational adjustment among secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

This study found a statistically significant positive relationship between parental involvement, self-concept and educational adjustment among secondary school students. Students who experiences higher level of parental involvement stands to have a better self concept and both parental involvement and self-concept play important roles in a student's educational adjustment.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of this study have significant implications for the field of education, indicating that parental involvement and self-concept have a substantial impact on the educational adjustment of secondary school students. Stronger parental involvement and a positive self concept are linked to better educational adjustment.

This suggests that efforts to enhance educational outcomes should focus on promoting greater parental involvement and cultivating positive self-concept in students. It is important to encourage parents to take an active role in their children's education. This could involve regular communication with teachers, participation in school events, or providing support with homework and learning at home.

Schools should introduce initiatives to encourage positive self-concept among students. This might include activities that boost self-esteem, self-confidence and a positive attitude towards learning. Collaboration between educators, parents, and mental health professionals is essential to create a supportive environment that addresses both educational and socio-emotional needs, ultimately promoting holistic adolescent development.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adeyemi, B. A., Adediran, V. O., & Adewole, O. S. (2018). Influence of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupils' adjustment in lower primary schools in Osun State. *International Journal of Humanities social science and education*, 5(4), 67-75.
- [2] Bhagat, P. (2017). Educational-adjustment and self-efficacy of secondary school students in relation to their gender and type of school. *International Journal of research in Social Sciences*, 7(5), 469-480.
- [3] Gupta, G. & Priyanka (2022). A Comparative Study of Self-Concept of Male and Female Secondary Students of Panipat District. *International Journal of Indian psychology*, 10(3).
- [4] Khan, A., & Alam, S. (2015). Self-Concept in Relation to Achievement Motivation of High School Students. *The International Journal of Indian psychology*, 2(4), B00305V2I42015. Retrieved from <http://www.ijip.in>
- [5] Monisha, B., & Vaidharani, V. S. (2024). Parental involvement and academic stress among higher secondary school students in Chennai district. *International Journal of creative research (IJCRT)* 12(1), e242. Retrieved from <http://www.ijcrt.org/volume12/issue1/ijcrt2401508.pdf>
- [6] Sekar, J., & Lawrence, A. S. (2016). Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment of Higher Secondary School Students in Relation to Academic Achievement. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 10(1), 29-35.
- [7] Shao, M., He, W., Zhao, L., & Su, Y. S. (2022). The influence of parental involvement on parent satisfaction: The moderating effect of parental educational level and the number of children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 752802.
- [8] Singh, M., & Mahajan, P. (2021). Parental involvement and academic achievement: a study on senior secondary students. *UGC Care Listed Journal*, 8(29), 122-129.
- [9] Rajkumari, Dr., & Babita, Ms. (2021). A study of educational adjustment in relation to self-efficacy of secondary school students. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary (IJMR)*, 7(10), 228. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra2013>.
- [10] Tiwari, N. S., & Tiwari, S. K. (2020). Relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement in higher secondary school students. *IJARIE*, 6(6), 90-96.

Citation: Shilpa, Poonam, Sandhya, Sushil Kumar, Exploring the Relationship Between Parental Involvement and Self-Concept in Secondary School Students and Its Influence on Educational Adjustment, *International Journal of Education (IJE)*, 5(1), 2024, pp. 24-32.

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJE_5_01_003

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJE/VOLUME_5_ISSUE_1/IJE_05_01_003.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com